

The Role of Psychological Factors in the Successful Digital Transformation of an Organization in Reducing Burnout Among Social Workers (Using Teachers as an Example)

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Abstract

This study examines the issue of teacher burnout and analyzes the psychological factors that contribute to successful digital transformation and its reduction. The authors drew on the resource conservation model of burnout (Hobfoll 2001), the model of psychological factors of successful digital transformation in the workplace (Trenerry et al. 2021), and theories of group norms (Terry et al. 1999; Smith and Louis 2009) to test the effects of individual-, group-, and organizational-level factors on reducing teacher burnout in educational organizations.

The study sample included teachers from small towns and rural areas in Russia (N = 316). Using structural equation modeling, we found that administrative support, an organizational-level factor, had a direct effect on reducing teacher burnout. Affective (emotional) readiness for the implementation of digital technologies also contributed to a reduction in teacher burnout. The group-level psychological factor – methodological support from specialist – did not have a significant effect on reducing teacher burnout. Similarly, the organizational-level psychological factor of perceiving digitalization as an organizational norm did not have a direct effect on reducing teacher burnout.

However, an indirect (mediating) effect of this factor was identified through the affective component of readiness for digitalization. It can be concluded that when digitalization is perceived by teachers as the norm, this generally enhances their positive attitude and motivation to use digital technologies in their professional activities, which ultimately leads to a decrease in burnout.

Keywords

digitalization as an organizational norm, administrative support, methodological support, readiness for digitalization, model of psychological factors of digital transformation, burnout, teachers

JEL codes: O33; I1

Introduction

The problem of employee burnout remains one of the most pressing issues in human resource management within modern organizations. In addressing this issue, it is essential to understand which factors associated with digital transformation – manifesting at different levels (individual, group, and organizational) – can serve as resources for mitigating negative manifestations in employee behavior and well-being and thereby reduce burnout. The present study aims to address this problem.

Digital transformation and burnout among social workers

In Russia, the national program “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation” is being actively implemented. It is designed to ensure the accelerated adoption of digital technologies in both the economic and social spheres (O nacional’nykh celyakh i strategicheskikh zadachakh razvitiya... 2024), thereby promoting the broader digitalization of society.

Experts studying digitalization processes in organizations (Antonova 2022; Vial 2019) note that its highest level corresponds to digital transformation. At the initial stage, an organization undergoes digitization, which involves converting and storing analog data (e.g., paper documents) in digital form. The next stage, digitalization, focuses on automating processes and operations, as well as enhancing information processing. Finally, digital transformation entails the creation of an entirely new organizational model based on digital information and technologies (Savić 2019).

At its core, digital transformation involves improving an organization through the integration of information, computing, communication, and network technologies, leading to a reorganization of its structure. Thus, digital transformation represents profound structural changes driven by new digital technologies that significantly affect the identity, values, and norms of both the organization and its employees (Wessel et al. 2021). In this context, the changes currently taking place in organizations within the social sector can be characterized as a form of digital transformation (Matyushkina et al. 2021; Merzlyakova 2022).

The success of digital transformation largely depends on the involvement and support of an organization’s employees. This underscores the growing need for specialists who are prepared to implement digital technologies, possess a sufficiently high level of digital competence, and are capable of coping with the potential negative consequences of digital transformation. Among these negative consequences, researchers (Polyakova 2021; Rambler News 2024; Khakimova et al. 2022) highlight technostress, which can lead to professional burnout.

Since 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) has officially recognized burnout as an occupational phenomenon characterized by mental and emotional exhaustion, increased negativity and cynicism toward one’s work, and a decline in professional efficacy (WHO 2019). The phenomenon of burnout has been actively studied since the 1980s (Maslach and Jackson 1986). Currently, several conceptual models of burnout exist (Maslach and Jackson 1986; Golembiewski and Munzenrider 1991; Vodopyanova 2011). One of the earliest and most influential, Maslach’s three-dimensional model, identifies three key components of burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment (Maslach and Jackson 1986). Other researchers, such as Perlman and Hartman (1982), have developed process models that conceptualize burnout as a phenomenon that develops through distinct phases over time.

Since the focus of our study is the successful digital transformation of organizations – which inherently presupposes employee well-being – the most relevant burnout models for our analysis are resource-based frameworks that help identify factors minimizing the negative effects of digitalization: the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model (Bakker and Demerouti 2017) and the Conservation of Resources (COR) model (Hobfoll 2001). In this study, we draw primarily on C. Hobfoll’s model, as it not only emphasizes the role of individual resources in overcoming burnout but also highlights the importance of the organizational context in maintaining employee well-being.

In Russian research traditions, burnout is conceptualized as both emotional and professional in nature (Boyko 1999; Skugarevskaya 2003). Within the framework of this study, workplace burnout – arising from the specific characteristics of professional activity and organizational conditions – is of particular relevance (Vodopyanova 2011). In this context, burnout is understood as emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion resulting from prolonged emotional stress, developing across three levels: individual, interpersonal, and organizational (Orel 2005).

As numerous studies have shown (Global Human Capital Trends 2014; Bradford 2018; Oleshko 2019), the consequences of digitalization – such as information overload resulting from continuous exposure to mobile applications, emails, and instant messaging; lack of time; constant availability; and work overload – significantly increase burnout among specialists in the social sector.

Research conducted in Russia among professionals such as doctors, journalists, bank employees, and teachers indicates that more than half of respondents experience symptoms of burnout related to digitalization. For instance, 75.5% of surveyed banking employees demonstrated high or moderate levels of emotional exhaustion (Mikhailova and Chizhevsky 2020). Similarly, 60% of physicians were found to exceed normative levels on the dimensions of tension, resistance, and exhaustion (Bodagova and Govorin 2013; Mikov et al. 2018).

Studies focusing on teachers have revealed that the introduction of digital technologies contributes to increased feelings of disappointment, life dissatisfaction, depression, and anxiety (Merzlyakova 2022; Khakimova et al. 2022). Surveys among teachers also show that they most frequently display the symptoms of burnout described as “inadequate selective emotional response” and “expansion of the sphere of emotional economy.” Teachers tend to avoid or minimize those aspects of their work that require significant emotional engagement (Khakimova et al. 2022).

Overall, it can be concluded that digital transformation contributes to burnout among both social workers in general and teachers in particular. Most often, the negative emotional consequences associated with digitalization include anxiety, depression, and emotional exhaustion. Moreover, burnout can manifest itself at the individual, interpersonal, and organizational levels. To identify the factors that can help reduce burnout, the resource-based model proposed by Hobfoll (2001) is particularly relevant, as it enables the analysis of both individual and organizational contextual factors.

The Role of Individual, Group, and Organizational Psychological Factors of Digital Transformation in Overcoming Employee Burnout

In this study, we draw on the Multi-Level Model of Psychological and Socio-Psychological Factors of Digital Transformation in the Workplace developed by Trenerry et al. (2021). This model considers factors at three levels – individual, group, and organizational – and focuses

specifically on those that contribute to successful digital transformation. This multi-level approach enables us to examine the problem of reducing burnout through the resource perspective, which aligns with our theoretical understanding of burnout (Vodopyanova 2011; Orel 2005; Hobfoll 2001).

Based on an extensive analysis of prior research, Trenerry et al. (2021) identified a range of psychological factors that operate at each level. At the *individual level*, these include technology acceptance and adaptation, perceptions and attitudes toward technological change, skills and abilities, as well as resilience and adaptability in the workplace, work stress, and psychological well-being. The *group level* comprises factors such as communication and collaboration within teams, team relationships and identification, and team resilience and adaptability. Finally, the *organizational level* involves factors such as leadership, human resource management practices, and organizational culture and climate.

An analysis of the existing literature shows that the issue of acceptance of digitalization and attitudes toward the implementation of digital technologies within organizations – an individual-level factor – has not yet been sufficiently explored. Most previous studies have primarily focused on the positive or negative attitudes toward digitalization and on the readiness to implement digital technologies among professionals in the social sector (Blease et al. 2018; Tasdogan 2020; Mercader and Gairín 2020; Soldatova and Shlyapnikov 2015; Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020).

A large-scale study conducted among healthcare workers across 43 regions of Russia identified five indicators of digital readiness: information literacy, communication and interaction, digital content creation, security, and problem-solving skills. According to the survey results, most physicians demonstrated intermediate to advanced levels of digital readiness. They reported being willing to help others improve their digital skills, expressed openness to sharing digital content, recognized the benefits of remote collaboration, and showed critical awareness of information in online communities. However, the respondents also expressed caution toward experimenting with new digital devices and programs, such as those involving artificial intelligence (Bezzubtseva et al. 2022).

A study of digital readiness conducted among teachers in St. Petersburg (Matyushkina et al. 2021) identified three types of readiness:

1. **Theoretical readiness**, which encompasses knowledge of key trends and characteristics of the current stage of development within one's industry, as well as sufficient understanding of digital resources, security, and related areas.
2. **Practical readiness**, reflected in hands-on experience with digital environments, proficiency in using various digital tools, and competence in digital security skills.
3. **Personal readiness**, defined as a positive attitude toward transformation processes associated with digitalization and a willingness to engage in such processes.

Further research employing the adapted and validated Technology Readiness Index 2.0 (TRI 2.0) (Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020) identified three core belief indicators underlying technological readiness: optimism, innovativeness, and negative attitudes toward technology. Survey results indicated that Russian teachers demonstrate an above-average level of technological readiness and are generally optimistic about digital technologies; however, their innovativeness was found to be slightly below average.

However, studies conducted among teachers in small towns and rural areas in Russia show somewhat different results. These teachers are often characterized by a deficit of digital skills and competencies and a low level of technological readiness (Zair-Bek et al. 2021; Ignatiev 2021). This is partly attributable to objective conditions and the uneven implemen-

tation of digital technologies in education. According to monitoring data from the National Research University Higher School of Economics, rural schools lag behind urban schools on almost all indicators reflecting the integration of digital technologies into general education institutions (Zair-Bek et al. 2021). Given this trend, studying the readiness of rural school teachers to implement digital technologies is particularly relevant.

From the perspective that an attitude is considered a predisposition to behave in a certain way, formed on the basis of acquired social experience, as well as a person's positive or negative evaluation of an object or phenomenon (Allport 1972), it can be assumed that readiness to implement digital technologies can be conceptualized as an attitude. However, a review of the literature indicates that prior studies have focused either on beliefs and emotional attitudes (i.e., the cognitive and affective components) (Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020) or on theoretical, practical, and personal readiness (Matyushkina et al. 2021). There are currently no studies that analyze all three components of attitude simultaneously: affective, cognitive, and behavioral. This study aims to fill this gap by demonstrating that a positive attitude, encompassing the affective, cognitive, and behavioral components, contributes to successful digital transformation and can serve as a resource for reducing burnout.

Among the group-level factors identified in the literature, support and effective interaction with digital technology specialists (i.e., the communication and collaboration factor) stand out. Effective interaction and communication between employees facilitate the flow of information, the exchange of knowledge and ideas, and the integration of tasks. In turn, this serves as a support mechanism for employees and enhances task coordination, collective decision-making, and the clarification of misunderstandings (Fletcher and Major 2006).

Furthermore, multi-level studies (Guinan et al. 2019; Merschbrock and Munkvold 2015) have highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary team collaboration, as it allows employees to receive support from specialists with diverse backgrounds and expertise, which is a critical lever for successful digital transformation.

Research conducted among Russian teachers indicates that effective interaction with digital technology specialists and methodological support help mitigate the negative consequences of digitalization, contribute to teachers' psychological well-being, and reduce burnout (Boronenko and Fedotova 2021; Tarasova et al. 2021). These findings suggest that methodological support from digital transformation specialists – which encompasses effective interaction, communication, knowledge and experience sharing, and clarification of misunderstandings – can play a key role in reducing burnout.

In addition, studies have demonstrated that specialist support, experience exchange in online communities, and methodological assistance also influence teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies (Boronenko and Fedotova 2021). Thus, a group-level factor such as methodological support from specialists can affect an individual-level factor, namely, the readiness (attitude) to implement digital technologies.

Among the organizational-level factors, researchers emphasize support from administration, often referred to as responsive leadership (Dery et al. 2017). For successful digital transformation, it is essential that managers foster a positive digital culture, motivate employees to embrace change and enhance their skills, engage digital experts, and provide employees with constructive feedback (Dery et al. 2017; Haddud and McAllen 2018).

Conversely, a lack of administrative support can act as a barrier to the implementation of digital technologies in education and may contribute to teacher burnout (Hepp et al. 2015). For example, a study conducted among teachers in St. Petersburg reported that 86% of respondents felt supported by their administration, which positively impacted their work

(Metodicheskie rekomendacii po formirovaniyu cifrovoj ... 2022). Based on these findings, it can be hypothesized that administrative support, reflecting responsive leadership, may help reduce teacher burnout.

Moreover, research shows that management support motivates employees to embrace digital transformation. Responsive leaders focus on the employee experience, actively engage with staff, promote skill development, encourage experimentation with new technologies, and provide resources and opportunities for continuous learning (Dery et al. 2017). A study conducted among Russian teachers further noted that the leadership of educational institutions plays a crucial role in enhancing digital literacy and developing various forms of teacher readiness for the implementation of digital technologies (Matyushkina et al. 2021).

Thus, it can be concluded that the organizational-level factor of administrative support has a positive effect on employees' readiness to implement digital technologies.

Among the psychological factors at the organizational level of digital transformation, organizational culture and climate have been studied extensively (Dery et al. 2017; Chanias et al. 2019). Initiating changes in organizational culture through effective communication, employee workshops on new digital technologies, and informal interactions such as "fire-side chats" can facilitate the change process and improve employee well-being (Chanias et al. 2019).

A study conducted in Russian companies (Kabalina et al. 2023) demonstrated that the organizational climate factor with the most significant impact on employee burnout is transformational leadership, which influences all three components of burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and perceived personal accomplishment. Additionally, research indicates that emotional exhaustion is largely shaped by the organization of work itself. However, as these findings were obtained in the manufacturing sector, it remains important to investigate whether they are applicable to employees in the social sector.

An analysis of definitions and concepts of organizational climate (Ehrhart et al. 2013; Hoßbach 2019; Schneider 1972; Parygin 1981; Pochebut and Chiker 2020) indicates that organizational norms are a key indicator. Some authors (Duerr et al. 2018; Serpa et al. 2022) even consider "digital" goals and norms as an integral level of organizational culture. Indeed, according to theories of group social norms, such norms are important predictors that influence both attitudes and human behavior (Terry et al. 1999; Terry et al. 2001; Smith and Louis 2009). Numerous experimental studies (Smith and Louis 2009; Schultz et al. 2007) demonstrate that group norms predict the attitudes and behavior of group members and affect satisfaction with group involvement. This effect is particularly strong when norms are established by reference groups, significant others, or in-group representatives. Based on this evidence, it can be assumed that the perception of digitalization as an organizational norm may influence employees' attitudes toward digital transformation, which in turn may impact employee well-being and reduce burnout.

In summary, the literature indicates that burnout among social sector professionals may be exacerbated by the negative consequences of organizational digital transformation. However, certain psychological factors can act as resources to mitigate burnout. At the individual level, this factor is a positive attitude toward digital transformation; at the group level, it is employee support from digital technology specialists; and at the organizational level, it includes administrative support (responsive leadership) and the presence of a "digitalization norm." Previous studies have generally examined these fac-

tors separately or within manufacturing contexts, leaving open questions about their applicability in the social sector.

This study aims to address these gaps by testing previous findings on a sample of teachers, as well as by analyzing the relationships between individual-, group-, and organizational-level psychological factors.

Based on the above, *the research goal* is to identify the role of psychological factors of organizational digital transformation at the individual (attitude toward the implementation of digital technologies in professional activities), group (methodological support from specialists), and organizational (perception of digitalization as an organizational norm, administrative support) levels in reducing teacher burnout.

Research hypotheses

1. Individual-level hypothesis: teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies in their professional activities is negatively associated with teacher burnout.
2. Group-level hypothesis (burnout): methodological support from specialists predicts lower levels of teacher burnout.
3. Organizational-level hypothesis (burnout): perception of digitalization as a norm and administrative support are negatively associated with teacher burnout.
4. Group-level hypothesis (readiness): methodological support from specialists predicts teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies.
5. Organizational-level hypothesis (readiness): perception of digitalization as a norm and administrative support predict teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies.

Research methodology

Sample

The survey was conducted in 2023–2024. The questionnaire was distributed through social networks and teacher-specific chat groups. The total number of respondents was 316 (95.6% women), aged 20 to 73 years ($M = 44.6$, $SD = 11.35$). Participants included 26% city residents and 74% rural residents. Work experience ranged from 1 to 49 years ($M = 20.64$, $SD = 12.26$).

Regarding professional categories, 91 respondents (28.8%) held the highest category, 81 respondents (25.6%) held the first category, and 3 respondents (1%) held the second category. The remaining participants had no professional category. Most respondents were subject teachers ($\approx 96\%$), while 4% were educational psychologists, speech therapists, or other specialists.

Research Instruments

Burnout. Given that teachers often report depressive and anxious states, with emotional exhaustion being the most prominent (Merzlyakova 2022), this study used the “Emotional exhaustion” subscale from the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), adapted by N.E. Vodopyanova and E.S. Starchenkova (2008). The scale includes 7 items (e.g., “I feel exhausted at the end of the workday”). Factor analysis confirmed one factor ($R^2 = 74.36$) with excellent reliability ($\omega = 0.95$).

Readiness to implement digital technologies

This construct was measured using separate scales for the affective, cognitive, and behavioral components:

Affective component: 7 items measuring emotional attitudes toward digital technology adoption. Example (reverse-coded): “I am forced to use digital educational resources and technologies in the classroom.” $R^2 = 70.27$, $\omega = 0.93$.

Cognitive component: 5 items measuring knowledge and skills related to digital technology adoption. Example: “I quickly learn to use new digital resources and technologies in the educational process.” $R^2 = 64.11$, $\omega = 0.84$.

Behavioral component: 13 items measuring practical engagement with digital technologies. Example: “I know how to use digital educational resources in various educational activities.” $R^2 = 61.79$, $\omega = 0.94$.

Methodological support from specialists. Measured using 4 items (e.g., “Our educational institution has organized interaction between teachers and IT specialists”). $R^2 = 64.90$, $\omega = 0.875$.

Administrative support. Measured using 3 items assessing management encouragement and support (e.g., “The administration of our educational institution encourages knowledge sharing and helps to master new digital technologies”). $R^2 = 81.49$, $\omega = 0.89$.

Perception of digitalization as an organizational norm. Measured using 6 items (e.g., “In our educational institution, digital technologies occupy an important place in the educational process”). $R^2 = 70.55$, $\omega = 0.93$.

All scales used a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“completely disagree”) to 7 (“completely agree”).

Data Analysis. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), and McDonald’s omega to assess scale reliability. Correlation analysis, mediation analysis, and structural equation modeling (SEM) were used to test the hypothesized relationships. Data were processed using SPSS 19.0 and AMOS 20.

Research results

In the first stage of the analysis, we examined the mean values, standard deviations, and correlations among all study variables. The results are presented in Table 1.

The descriptive analysis indicated that teacher burnout (emotional exhaustion) was at an average level. Among the components of teachers’ readiness to implement digital technologies, the cognitive component was the most pronounced, followed by the affective component, while the behavioral component was the least pronounced. Teachers reported that administrative support at their institutions was high, and methodological support from specialists was also at a substantial level. The perception of digitalization as an organizational norm was similarly reported to be relatively high.

Preliminary correlation analysis revealed that burnout (emotional exhaustion) was negatively associated with the affective and cognitive components of readiness to implement digital technologies. Burnout was also negatively correlated with administrative support and the perception of digitalization as a norm. Additionally, the indicators of individual-level factors (affective, cognitive, and behavioral components of readiness) and organizational-level factors (administrative and methodological support, perception of digitalization as a norm) were positively interrelated.

Table 1. Mean values and correlation coefficients (min. 1, max. 7)

Nº	Variables	Average values	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Burnout (emotional exhaustion)	3.41	-0.18***	-0.13*	-0.09	-0.11	-0,17**	-0,17**
2	Affective component of readiness	5.65	1	0.72***	0.63***	0.44***	0.51***	0.82***
3	Cognitive component of readiness	5.74		1	0.55***	0.50***	0.53***	0.70***
4	Behavioral component of readiness	4.98			1	0.47***	0.51***	0.58***
5	Methodological support for specialists	5.08				1	0.68***	0.48***
6	Administration support	5.56					1	0.56***
7	Perception of digitalization as an organizational norm	5.70						1

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

To account for potential confounding effects, we controlled for gender, age, length of service, and professional category on teacher burnout. Regression analysis indicated that these variables explained only 2.6% of the variance in burnout and did not have a statistically significant effect.

We then tested the hypothesized relationships using structural equation modeling (SEM). The results are presented in Figure 1, with only significant coefficients shown. The model demonstrated good fit indices, consistent with recommended criteria (Hu and Bentler 1999): $\chi^2/df = 3.1$, $p = 0.001$, CFI = 0.99, SRMR = 0.02, RMSEA = 0.08, PCLOSE = 0.141.

These results indicate that the proposed multi-level model adequately represents the relationships among individual, group, and organizational psychological factors of digital transformation and their effects on teacher burnout and readiness.

We first examined the interrelations among indicators representing the individual-level psychological factor. The results showed that only the affective component of teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies had a direct negative effect on teacher burnout. This indicates that emotional exhaustion is reduced when teachers hold a positive attitude toward digital technologies and are willing to implement them in their professional activities.

Interestingly, neither the cognitive nor the behavioral components of digital readiness had a significant effect on reducing teacher burnout. This suggests that possessing knowledge, skills, or practical abilities related to digital technologies alone is insufficient to mitigate stress and burnout. Rather, it is internal acceptance, a positive perception of digitalization, and a genuine willingness to use digital technologies in one's work that contribute to overcoming burnout.

Thus, our first hypothesis was only partially supported, highlighting the critical role of the affective dimension of readiness in protecting teachers from burnout.

Figure 1. Path model of the relationships among individual-, group-, and organizational-level psychological factors of digital transformation and teacher burnout. Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$; † $p = 0.06$

At the group level, methodological support from specialists did not have a significant direct effect on teacher burnout. However, it was positively associated with the cognitive and behavioral components of teachers’ readiness to implement digital technologies in their professional activities. These findings do not support our second hypothesis, but they partially support the fourth hypothesis, indicating that methodological support enhances teachers’ readiness even if it does not directly reduce burnout.

At the organizational level, the perception of digitalization as an organizational norm did not have a direct, significant effect on teacher burnout. Mediation analysis, however, revealed a significant indirect effect via the affective component of readiness ($\beta = -0.07$, $p = 0.04$). This suggests that when teachers perceive digitalization as a norm within their institution, they develop a more positive attitude and willingness to use digital technologies, which ultimately contributes to a reduction in emotional exhaustion.

Administrative support, another organizational-level factor, was found to directly predict lower teacher burnout. This indicates that when teachers feel supported by management and perceive the administration as responsive to issues related to digital transformation, their emotional exhaustion decreases, providing partial support for our third hypothesis.

Further analyses showed that the perception of digitalization as an organizational norm is positively related to all three components of teachers’ readiness (affective, cognitive, and behavioral). In contrast, administrative support was positively associated only with the cognitive and behavioral components of readiness. These results provide partial support for our fifth hypothesis, highlighting the differential roles of organizational-level factors in shaping teacher readiness and mitigating burnout.

Additional analyses revealed significant positive correlations among the group- and organizational-level psychological factors. Specifically, the perception of digitalization as an

organizational norm, administrative support, and methodological support from specialists were all positively interrelated. Regarding teachers' readiness to implement digital technologies, a significant relationship was observed only between the affective and cognitive components.

Discussion of results and conclusion

This study aimed to identify psychological factors that can act as resources and reduce teacher burnout during the digital transformation of educational institutions. Our results showed that, overall, teachers in Russian schools exhibit an average level of burnout (emotional exhaustion). At the same time, they are generally ready to implement digital technologies in their activities, particularly in terms of knowledge. Similar findings have been reported by other researchers, who noted a not very high level of emotional burnout among school teachers and their readiness to adopt digital technologies, which are often considered by them as norms (Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020; Khakimova et al. 2022).

Teachers also indicated that they feel supported both by the administration and by colleagues – specifically, IT specialists. Comparable results were obtained in a study of teachers from schools in St. Petersburg and the Leningrad region, where 68% of teachers reported being satisfied with the support and assistance they received from school leadership (Matyushkina et al. 2021).

In our study, we found that only the affective component of teachers' readiness for digitalization was associated with reduced emotional exhaustion. This suggests that the most important factor is teachers' desire and perception of the significance of implementing digital technologies. The absence of fears, anxieties, and negative experiences regarding digital transformation appears to help reduce emotional burnout. These findings are partly consistent with previous studies, which showed that teachers' positive attitudes toward digitalization contribute to stress reduction and maintenance of health (Merzlyakova 2022).

However, our data did not reveal a significant relationship between teachers' knowledge of digital technologies or their skills, expressed as readiness at the cognitive and behavioral levels, and burnout. This suggests that reducing burnout requires more than high digital competence alone. In this respect, our results diverge somewhat from previous studies (Matyushkina et al. 2021; Merzlyakova 2022; Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020; Khakimova et al. 2022). This discrepancy may be due to our focus on emotional exhaustion, whereas cognitive and behavioral readiness may predominantly influence other burnout dimensions, such as depersonalization and perceived personal achievement. This assumption, however, requires further verification.

Our research showed that the most important factor directly reducing teacher burnout is support from the educational institution's administration. When leaders are responsive to teachers' concerns about digitalization, organize effective communication, hold joint seminars, and provide positive feedback, teachers are less likely to experience burnout. These results are consistent with findings from companies (Dery et al. 2017) and underscore the importance of "responsive leadership" as an organizational-level psychological factor for the successful digital transformation of educational institutions.

We did not find a significant direct effect of methodological support from specialists on reducing emotional burnout. It is possible that this factor operates indirectly, for example, through the support of the administration. This assumption requires further investigation.

Regarding the perception of digitalization as an organizational norm, no direct effect on teacher burnout was identified. However, our data showed an indirect effect via the affective component of readiness. This suggests that when teachers embrace digitalization and perceive it as a norm within their educational organization, their emotional readiness and willingness to adhere to this norm increase, which in turn reduces negative experiences and helps overcome emotional exhaustion. These findings are consistent with general theories on the relationship between group norms, attitudes, and behavior (Terry et al. 2001; Terry et al. 1999; Smith and Louis 2009). They also align with Russian studies of teachers (Khakimova et al. 2022), which indicate that organizational conditions may not always be directly related to teacher burnout but can be mediated by teachers' beliefs and attitudes.

Our research further showed that psychological factors of successful digital transformation at the individual, group, and organizational levels are interconnected. Teachers' perception of digitalization as a norm positively influences all three components of their readiness to implement digital technologies. Support from the administration and methodological support from specialists positively affected the cognitive and behavioral components of readiness. This result is logical, as such forms of support in educational organizations typically address teachers' challenges in acquiring knowledge, applying skills, and implementing digital technologies in practice. These findings are consistent with previous studies conducted among teachers in Russian schools (Matyushkina et al. 2021; Merzlyakova 2022; Khavenson and Gizatullin 2020).

Conclusion

In summary, it is important to establish a digitalization standard in educational institutions, as this minimizes fears, encourages teachers to embrace digitalization and prepare for its implementation, and reduces burnout. Support from the administration and responsiveness to requests for solutions to digital transformation issues are also crucial for reducing teacher burnout.

The results of this study may be useful to heads of educational institutions. This study extends the applicability of the “Multi-level model of psychological and socio-psychological factors of digital transformation in the workplace” (Trenerry et al. 2021) to social professionals, namely educators. Additionally, the obtained results complement the organizational-level factors in this model by including “digitalization as an organizational norm.” Overall, the findings provide a deeper understanding of the factors that reduce the risks of digitalization for social sector professionals.

We acknowledge several *limitations* of this study. First, the factors identified explain only 7% of the variance in teacher burnout, indicating that their overall effect is modest. Although teachers report that digital transformation has negative consequences affecting burnout, other issues, such as relationships with children and parents or the implementation of new programs and standards, may have a greater impact. Second, we did not account for the degree of digital transformation in educational organizations. Our study primarily involved teachers from small towns and rural areas, and the situation in large cities and metropolitan areas, where unified platforms such as the Moscow Electronic School (MES) are actively used, may differ significantly. Third, we focused on selected psychological factors and examined only one aspect of burnout – emotional exhaustion.

Therefore, further research is needed, for example, to compare the effects of organizational culture, group factors, and readiness for digitalization on emotional burnout among teachers in large cities, small towns, and rural areas.

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